

Attenuation of the toxic effects of bromobenzene on the kidneys in Wistar albino rats by the blue green algae *Spirulina fusiformis*

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Abstract : The present study was aimed to assess the nephroprotective role of *Spirulina fusiformis* on bromobenzene (BB) induced toxicity in rat kidneys. Female Wistar rats were treated with a single oral dose of BB (10 mmol/kg/b.w.) following the oral administration of *Spirulina fusiformis* (400 and 800 mg kg/b.w.) for 8 days. The levels of serum renal function markers (creatinine, urea, total protein, albumin, acid phosphatase) and serum apoptotic markers (Tumour necrosis factor-alpha and Interleukin-1 beta) in the experimental animals were measured and compared with that of the normal control and the standard drug silymarin treated groups. The BB treated group showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in the levels of serum total protein and albumin and a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in the levels of serum creatinine, urea, acid phosphatase, Tumour necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) and Interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β). The results of the kidney histopathological examination further confirm the nephroprotective role of *Spirulina fusiformis*. Furthermore, the active components of *Spirulina fusiformis* such as betacarotene, 3Z-phycoyanobilin and vitamin B12 were docked with TNF- α and IL-1 β . Vitamin B12 showed highest number of hydrogen bonds and betacarotene showed significant geometric fit indicating significant interactions with TNF- α and IL-1 β . The results of the present study indicate the nephroprotective role of *Spirulina fusiformis* in female Wistar albino rats.

Keywords : Bromobenzene, nephrotoxicity, cytokines, *Spirulina fusiformis*, docking.

Introduction

Bromobenzene is an industrial chemical used as an additive in motor oil and as a solvent for large scale crystallizations. Human exposure to this xenobiotic is by ingestion of contaminated food or inhalation of air contaminated with bromobenzene¹. The metabolites of BB are known to conjugate with glutathione leading to depletion of antioxidant status in the kidneys².

The blue green algae *Spirulina* is known for its beneficial effects when taken as a food supplement. It is a rich source of protein, vitamins, minerals and beta-carotenes³. Multiple studies assessing the protective role of this alga have shown that it is useful in treating chronic fatigue, rhinitis, allergy, viral infections and chronic arsenic poisoning⁴⁻⁶.

Experimental

Animals :

Female Wistar albino rats weighing 132 ± 14 g were acquired from the animal house, VIT University, Vellore,

India. The animals were maintained in a light and temperature controlled room with a 12 h dark/light cycle. The rats were allowed access to standard pelleted rat feed and water *ad libitum*.

Chemicals :

BB was purchased from Sigma Aldrich, India and *Spirulina fusiformis* was purchased from Acumen Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd., Pondicherry. The standard drug Silymarin was purchased locally. All other reagents used in this study were standard laboratory reagents of analytical grade and were purchased locally. The Uristix strips for quantitative determination of urinary protein were obtained from Siemens, India.

Experimental design :

The experimental rats were randomly divided into 5 groups of 6 animals each. Group 1 (normal control) rats were administered 1 ml coconut oil orally; Group 2 were administered BB (10 mmol in 1 ml coconut oil) orally; Group 3 rats were administered *Spirulina fusiformis* (400

mg/kg b.w.) orally for 8 days prior to BB administration on the last day; Group 4 were administered *Spirulina fusiformis* (800 mg/kg b.w.) orally for 8 days prior to BB administration on the last day; Group 5 were administered silymarin (100 mg/kg b.w.) for 8 days prior to BB administration. The blood and kidneys of the animals were collected by sacrificing the animals 19 h after the administration of BB on the last day.

Serum renal function markers :

The levels of creatinine, urea, total protein and albumin were determined in the serum of experimental animals using commercial diagnostic kits purchased from Autospan Diagnostics, India. The parameters were tested according to the manufacturer's protocol. Acid phosphatase was estimated by the method of King⁷.

Serum apoptotic markers :

The levels of serum apoptotic markers TNF- α and IL-1 β were measured using ELISA kits purchased from Krishgen Biosystems, India according to the manufacturer's protocol.

Histopathological examination :

The kidney tissues were fixed in 10% formalin immediately after sacrifice. After treatment with descending grades of isopropanol the tissues were treated with xylene and embedded in molten paraffin wax. Tissue sections of about 5 μ m thickness were cut using microtome. Staining was done with Haematoxylin and Eosin. The sections were examined microscopically for histological changes.

In silico binding and interaction analysis :

The pdb structures of TNF- α (1TNF) and IL-1 β

(2MIB) were obtained from RCSB protein databank (www.rcsb.org/pdb/home/home.do) (Fig. 1). The receptor molecules were processed to remove water molecules and ligands before docking. The pdb structures of the active components of *Spirulina fusiformis* (betacarotene,

Fig. 1. 3D-structures of 1TNF and 2MIB.

3Z-phycoerythrin and vitamin B12) were generated by submitting the corresponding SMILES of the compounds obtained from www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pccompound to CORINA Molecular Networks (www.molecular-networks.com/online_demos/corina_demo) (Fig. 2). The docking experiments were carried out by submitting the receptor and ligand pdb files on PatchDock server for molecular docking and the docked complexes were analysed using PyMOL molecular viewer.

Results and discussion

Effect of Spirulina fusiformis on serum renal functional markers :

Elevated levels of serum creatinine and urea were seen in the BB-treated group indicating tubular dysfunction. These were brought to near normal levels by the oral administration of *Spirulina fusiformis* (Table 1).

Fig. 2. Structures of the ligands.

Table 1. Effect of *Spirulina fusiformis* on serum in BB intoxicated rats

Parameters	Group I	Group II	Group III	Group IV	Group V
Creatinine (mg/dl)	0.56 ± 0.03	4.12 ± 0.84 a*	0.74 ± 0.09 b*	0.69 ± 0.06 b*	0.77 ± 0.09 b*
Urea (mg/dl)	23.57 ± 1.04	41.78 ± 1.26 a*	25.12 ± 1.02 b*	24.86 ± 1.02 b*	27.62 ± 0.98 a*b*
Total protein (g/dl)	6.24 ± 0.87	4.02 ± 0.61 a*	5.56 ± 0.68 b*	5.89 ± 0.73 b*	5.34 ± 0.68 b*
Albumin (g/dl)	4.35 ± 0.36	2.86 ± 0.21 a*	3.96 ± 0.35 b*	4.28 ± 0.38 b*	4.11 ± 0.34 b*
Acid phosphatase (mg/dl)	0.15 ± 0.03	0.36 ± 0.06 a*	0.18 ± 0.02 b*	0.16 ± 0.02 b*	0.18 ± 0.03 b*

N = 6 animals in each group. The values are expressed as mean ± S.D. Comparisons indicated by lower case letters were made as follows : a – group I vs group II, III, IV and V; b – group II vs group III, IV and V; c – group III vs group IV and V; d – group IV vs group V. Statistical analysis was done by one way ANOVA followed by Student's Newman-Kuel's test. The symbols represent statistical significance at : **p* < 0.05.

BB intoxicated rats also showed a significant (*p* < 0.05) decrease in the levels of serum total protein and albumin (Table 1). Protein was also found in the urine of the BB intoxicated rats by a semi-quantitative strip method (Table 2). These results are indicative of the loss of protein through the renal system showing impaired glomerular filtration in the BB-treated animals⁸. This was reversed in the animals treated with *Spirulina fusiformis* in a dose dependent manner which was comparable with that of the standard drug treated group. This damage to nephrons is further established by the significant (*p* < 0.05) increase in the levels of acid phosphatase in the serum of BB-treated rats. Acid phosphatase a lysosomal enzyme finds its way into the circulation due to renal tissue necrosis⁹.

Table 2. Semi-quantitative determination of urinary protein in the experimental rats

Experimental groups	Protein
Group I	Nil
Group II	+++
Group III	Nil
Group IV	Nil
Group V	Nil

Effect of Spirulina fusiformis on the levels of serum apoptotic markers TNF-α and IL-1β :

TNF-α and IL-1β are members of the cytokine fa-

mily. TNF-α is mainly released by activated macrophages and is involved in the regulation of cells of the immune system being capable of inducing apoptotic cell death¹⁰. IL-1β is another important member of the cytokine family which mediates inflammatory response and apoptosis¹¹. TNF-α enhances phagocytosis by the macrophages and also stimulates the production of IL-1β. Therefore the elevated levels of TNF-α and IL-1β in the serum of the experimental rats in the present study are an indication of apoptotic cell death (Fig. 3). These two cytokines were found to be near to normal levels in the *Spirulina fusiformis* treated rats.

Fig. 3. Effect of *Spirulina fusiformis* on the levels of serum apoptotic markers (TNF-α and IL-1β).

Effects of Spirulina fusiformis on the histology of BB-intoxicated rat kidneys :

The kidneys of the normal control rats show normal

histology while that of the BB-intoxicated rats show severe renal tubular damage. The kidneys sections of the group 3 rats (BB + *Spirulina fusiformis* 400 mg/kg b.w./day) show normal morphology which is comparable with the normal control. There is tubular oedema seen in the kidney sections of group 4 rats (BB + *Spirulina fusiformis* 800 mg/kg b.w./day) which could be due to the effect of higher drug dosage. The standard drug treated rats show very mild tubular damage. Therefore, *Spirulina fusiformis* at a dose of 400 mg/kg b.w./day is able to restore normal kidney morphology in BB-treated rats.

Results and analysis of molecular docking studies :

The scores of the docked complexes and their ACE (Atomic Contact Energy) are shown in Table 3. Among

Table 3. Scores and ACE of the docked complexes

Receptor PDB Id	Ligand	Score	ACE
1TNF	Beta carotene	7000	-213.26
1TNF	3Z-Phycocyanobilin	5978	-157.50
1TNF	Vitamin B12	9012	-229.79
2MIB	Beta carotene	5610	-337.65
2MIB	3Z-Phycocyanobilin	5074	-183.48
2MIB	Vitamin B12	6606	-231.58

the selected active components of *Spirulina fusiformis* vitamin B12 shows significant binding and interactions with both TNF- α and IL-1 β . Out of the three ligands used in this study vitamin B12 is the only active component showing hydrogen bonding with both the cytokines. Beta carotene is a well-known and potent antioxidant which is proven to ameliorate oxidative stress in rats¹². This active component did not form any hydrogen bonds with both the cytokines but showed significant binding with a good geometric fit as it shows the lowest ACE (-337.65) among the 6 docked complexes. The interactions of the selected ligands with the cytokines TNF- α and IL-1 β are shown in Fig. 4.

TNF is the most effective cytokine in inducing apoptosis and is involved in both cell survival and cell death mechanisms of which the latter is regulated by the activation of caspases¹³. IL-1 β induces pro-apoptotic signals and is cytotoxic along with TNF- α or IFN- γ ¹⁴. Therefore, the results of the molecular docking experiments carried out in this study correlate with the reduction in the levels of these two serum apoptotic markers (TNF- α and IL-1 β) in BB-intoxicated rats on treatment with *Spirulina fusiformis*.

Fig. 4. (a) Control, normal kidney showing glomerulus. (b) BB-treated (10 mmol/kg b.w.) group, severe renal tubular damage. (c) BB + *Spirulina* 400 mg/kg b.w., normal kidney morphology with mild congestion. (d) BB + *Spirulina* 800 mg/kg b.w., showing tubular oedema. (e) BB + Silymarin (100 mg/kg b.w.) reference drug, normal kidney with mild tubular damage.

Fig. 4. Binding and interactions of the ligands with the cytokines TNF- α (1TNF) and IL-1 β (2MIB).

Conclusion

The present study indicates the potential role of *Spirulina fusiformis* in normalizing the levels of serum creatinine, urea, total protein, albumin and acid phosphatase in BB intoxicated rats. These effects could be due to the rich content of beta-carotenes which are well known antioxidants. Furthermore, the elevated levels of cytokines (TNF- α and IL-1 β) were brought back to normal levels on treatment with *Spirulina fusiformis*. From the results of the molecular docking experiments, it is evident that vitamin B12 binds and interacts significantly with the cytokines (TNF- α and IL-1 β) forming hydrogen bonds while beta-carotene binds showing significant geometric fit.

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